

Supplement 4. Intraspecific activation energies (E_{intra} , eV) estimated from individual fits of growth rate $\sim$ temperature of each taxon of autotrophic and heterotrophic protists.

Fig. S1. Growth rate versus temperature plots for each autotrophic taxon